

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
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TRANSPORT DECARBONIZATION STRATEGY

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Abstract: The article provides an overview of the research of foreign scientists on the issues of decarbonization of transport, competition for alternative fuels and between alternative modes of transport. The paper formulates decarbonization strategies and substantiates the main objectives of approaches to decarbonization of transport. In conclusion, the authors recommend ways to reduce greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions in transport as part of the decarbonization of the economy.

Key words: sustainable development, transport, logistics, transport policy, strategy, ecology, government regulation, decarbonization, carbon footprint, greenhouse gas.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada chet ellik olimlarning transportni karbonsizlantirish, muqobil yoqilg'i uchun raqobat va muqobil transport turlari o'rtasidagi raqobatni tadqiqotlari haqida umumiy ma'lumot berilgan. Maqolada dekarbonizatsiya strategiyasi shakllantirilgan va transportni dekarbonizatsiya qilish yondashuvlarining asosiy maqsadlari asoslangan. Xulosa qilib aytganda, mualliflar iqtisodiyotni dekarbonizatsiya qilishning bir qismi sifatida transportda issiqxona gazlari (IG) chiqindilarini kamaytirish usullarini tavsiya qildilar.

Kalit so'zlar: barqaror rivojlanish, transport, logistika, transport siyosati, strategiya, ekologiya, davlat tomonidan tartibga solish, dekarbonizatsiya, uglerod izi, issiqxona gazlari.

Аннотация: В статье сделан обзор исследований зарубежных ученых по вопросам декарбонизации транспорта, конкуренции за альтернативные виды топлива и между альтернативными видами транспорта. В работе сформулированы стратегии декарбонизации, обоснованы основные цели подходов к декарбонизации транспорта. В заключении авторы рекомендуют направления снижения выбросов парниковых газов (ПГ) на транспорте в рамках декарбонизации экономики.

Ключевые слова: устойчивое развитие, транспорт, логистика, транспортная политика, стратегия, экология, государственное регулирование, декарбонизация, углеродный след, парниковые газы.

INTRODUCTION

The concept of sustainable transport has gained wide recognition as a goal and is featured in the environmental plans of many governments and corporations. For example, the European Union has set an ambitious target to reduce net greenhouse gas emissions by 55% by 2030 compared to 1990 levels. However, sustainable transport remains elusive as it does not offer clear guiding principles, but rather a narrative that allows stakeholders to remain vague in their commitments and initiatives. In the 17 Sustainable Development Goals defined by the United Nations, transport was not identified as a separate sustainable development goal, despite accounting for about a quarter of global CO₂ emissions.

Transport decarbonization aims to reduce, mitigate and even eliminate carbon emissions by adapting transport infrastructure, vehicles and operations.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Many studies on the decarbonization of the global transport sector argue that the transport sector is struggling to decarbonize and make its proportionate contribution to achieving the ambitious climate targets set by the Paris Agreement ^[1]. Analysis by Gota et al. (2019) shows that, in the absence of additional measures, emissions from the transport sector could exceed previous projections and thus pose a major obstacle to preventing dangerous climate change. However, if countries collectively put maximum effort into implementing comprehensive low-carbon measures, the sector could achieve emissions reductions approaching the 1.5 degree scenario. ^[2]

Naemeka et al (2022) argued that several studies have modeled different pathways for decarbonizing the transport system, but consensus remains unclear due to the heterogeneity of transport technologies, infrastructure, locations and consumers. The study shows that decarbonization of the transport sector poses challenges related to revenue generation, financing transition policies, competition for alternative fuels, displacement of low-income consumers and potential impacts on travel behavior. ^[3]

Danish scientists Kani et al. (2022) argue in their study that the transport sector accounts for approximately a third of Denmark's greenhouse gas emissions and almost half of the energy sector's emissions. Between 2030 and 2045, significant electrification of road transport and a focus on shifting mobility needs from roads to rail and bicycles will lead to complete decarbonization, as well as the substitution of fossil fuels for electric power in aviation, shipping and heavy-duty road transport. ^[4]

According to Chaundry et al (2022), decarbonization of heating systems and road transport are seen as necessary but very difficult steps towards zero carbon emissions. They described how a national gas and electricity transmission network model was expanded to represent multiple local energy systems and combined with a national energy demand and road transport model. While using hydrogen for heating and transportation spreads the costs of a hydrogen network across homeowners and motorists, overall it is still considered a more expensive option compared to an all-electric scenario. ^[5]

Tseiranaki et al (2023) analyzed historical trends in energy consumption in the EU road transport sector and considered the role of key factors such as economic and population growth, fuel prices, passenger volumes and tonne-kilometres, and vehicle fleet characteristics. In light of the EU's energy and climate targets for 2030 and 2050, the document assesses progress in energy efficiency and decarbonization from 2000 to 2018. ^[6]

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research methodology is based on systematic approaches to studying problems using statistical, heuristic methods and techniques for analyzing world practice in studying the principles of sustainable development of transport systems, as well as a model of transport decarbonization strategy.

RESEARCH RESULTS

Since the early 2000s, sustainable development goals in the transport sector have been revised towards a more tangible strategy focused on carbon consumption and emissions. This has largely shaped around the decarbonization of transport, which helps set the agenda on the role of fossil fuels. This concept does not undermine the purpose of transport, which is to ensure the mobility of passengers and goods, but that the carbon footprint of transport activities must be reduced. Even if it focuses on carbon, decarbonization directly impacts other externalities since most air pollutants are the result of burning fossil fuels. Three emissions areas have been proposed to formulate decarbonization strategies :

- **Scope 1 (Direct Emissions):** Carbon (and other greenhouse gases such as nitrogen oxide) emissions result from manufacturing activities. This applies in particular to vehicle emissions.
- **Scope 2 (Indirect Emissions):** Emissions resulting from the production of fuel and electricity for operations. Even electricity, which may not generate Scope 1 emissions, can generate Scope 2 emissions if it is generated by fossil fuels such as coal and natural gas.
- **Scope 3 (Indirect/Induced Emissions):** Emissions arising from activities upstream and downstream of the organization. These are the most difficult to estimate because they are not under the direct control of the organization producing Scope 1 and 2 emissions. These include emissions arising from management's business travel, employee commuting, waste generation and disposal, goods and ser-

services purchased by the organization, and transport and distribution services used for procurement and market access.

Energy, which accounted for 74 percent of Uzbekistan's greenhouse gas emissions in 2019, and agriculture, which accounted for 19 percent, are the most important sectors for the decarbonization of the economy. Energy, or the energy system, covers the entire value chain from the extraction of energy resources to their transformation (electricity, hydrogen, etc.) and use by major end users, including buildings, industry, agriculture and transport. ^[7]

Table 1 shows the pollutants emitted into the atmosphere in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2011-2022, which shows that by a large margin the region with the most polluted atmosphere is Tashkent. It is followed by the Kashkadarya region; in other regions, emissions of pollutants are significantly lower.

Transport decarbonization includes a variety of approaches that attempt to influence its economics, infrastructure, regulatory environment or innovative practices that rely on information technology. The main goals are:

- Reduction in overall passenger and freight traffic while mobility needs continue to be met.
- Transition to lower carbon emitting modes of transport. The goal is to meet mobility needs with modes of transport that are based on less carbon-intensive technologies or offer economies of scale (less carbon emissions per unit of passenger or cargo carried).
- Higher utilization of existing transport assets such as roads, terminals and vehicles. This way, the same assets can handle higher levels of mobility demand.
- Increasing the energy efficiency of vehicles and equipment. Each piece of passenger or freight cargo moves with less energy expended.

The push to decarbonize transport is largely focused on electrification, but transport modes such as air and sea will switch to alternative fuels such as LNG and ammonia. Sales of electric vehicles are growing rapidly, and as of 2022 they accounted for 14% of global sales. They accounted for about 5% of all automobile sales in the United States, 7% in China, and about 15% in most European countries (more than 70% in Norway). Electrification represents the temporary transfer of mobility to fundamental attributes such as reduced range (battery charge). This therefore means reduced flexibility and performance. This transition will likely continue until electric vehicles perform similarly to their combustion engine equivalents. Sustainability and decarbonization are part of the same agenda, the only difference being that decarbonization offers a clearer framework and action plan with practical solutions.

The NZE-2060 (Net Zero Emissions) scenario reflects a feasible path for the energy industry to achieve peak emissions by 2030 and decarbonize by 2060 at the lowest cost, while strengthening the country's energy independence. In the NBV 2060 scenario, energy security is enhanced, with net energy imports capped at 8 percent by 2060 as most energy is generated domestically. Domestic renewables will provide 70 percent of the energy supply from domestic sources by 2060, and more than 85 percent when combined with hydrogen and domestic production and generation. ^[7]

In order to reduce the negative impact of aviation on the global climate, states, the aviation industry and all other stakeholders through ICAO have been developing a set of measures to reduce CO₂ emissions for many years. These efforts have contributed to modern aircraft being 70% quieter and 80% more fuel efficient than their earlier predecessors. Achieving the global decarbonization needed to curb rising global temperatures now requires radical, disruptive, and in many cases revolutionary innovations in technology and flight operations. ^[8]

During 2020–2024, the number of passenger cars owned by private individuals has steadily increased. Thus, from 2020 to 2024, their number increased to 1 348.6 thousand units, or by 55.9% (fig.1).

The structure of passenger transportation by mode of transport shows that the share of road transport slightly decrease since 2019 to 2023 and now it compiles 97.2%. The positive trend is that the share of electric transport increases from 1,4% in 2019 to 2.6% in 2023 (fig.2).

Table or diagram

Table 1: Released to the atmosphere pollutants, thousand tons

Regions	2011	2013	2015	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
The Republic of Uzbekistan	788.2	855.2	975.1	853.5	883.7	952.8	924.4	908.7	874
Republic of Karakalpakstan	23.5	25.8	32.8	37.7	34.0	37.2	28.9	31.4	21
Andijan	13.6	14.4	18.5	15.8	15.9	14.3	11.5	4.9	17

Bukhara	71.7	50.7	55.6	63.8	74.8	69.1	37.1	44.7	36
Jizzakh	17.3	17.2	70.2	5.2	11.8	4.3	3.4	2.9	27
Kashkadarya	142.5	167.0	176.3	165.7	152.2	140.4	128.1	132.3	116
Navoi	45.2	43.9	47.0	44.1	49.9	43.6	48.4	68.6	42
Namangan	5.6	3.7	7.8	15.9	15.2	15.8	15.0	23.9	7
Samarkand	51.8	49.1	54.7	37.2	52.1	44.2	52.7	39.4	39
Surkhandarya	3.3	3.7	3.1	3.2	5.1	6.9	6.5	7.1	7
Syrdarya	58.7	35.4	66.1	59.6	60.5	47.8	71.8	45.7	49
Tashkent	280.3	372.3	370.6	302.9	336.6	397.9	430.0	425.5	438
Fergana	42.8	40.2	38.9	60.1	53.2	49.6	50.5	46.5	49
Khorezm	4.9	6.2	5.0	9.2	7.1	7.2	6.8	7.2	5
Tashkent	27.0	25.6	28.5	33.1	15.3	74.5	33.7	28.6	21

Fig.1: Number of passenger cars owned by individuals in the Republic of Uzbekistan (as of January 1, 2024, units)¹

Fig.2: Structure of passenger transportation by mode of transport for January-December (in %)

CONCLUSIONS

As a conclusion, the authors recommend the following directions for reducing greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions in transport within the framework of economic decarbonization:

- 1) Updating the existing fleet of vehicles;
- 2) Transition to cleaner energy sources;

¹ <https://stat.uz/en/quarterly-reports/39036-2023-eng-2#january-december>

- 3) A significant reduction in the movement of people around the city by transport due to smart planning of urban space (mixed zoning), the development of e-commerce;
- 4) Encouraging the urban population to switch from personal cars to public transport by improving the public transport infrastructure and improving the quality of service in public transport, developing a smart public transport system, as well as increasing the cost of using personal vehicles using methods such as increasing the cost of gasoline, parking, and road taxes and other measures.

Thus, the creation of specific measures and the development of a roadmap for the implementation of the above measures will contribute to a real reduction in the level of air pollution from transport.

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Yashil

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O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi rayosatining 2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-sonli qarori bilan ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

